

Cardamom Grading Using Convolutional Neural Network(CNN)

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Abstract— Cardamom grading is a crucial task in the spice industry, and automating it can significantly reduce the cost and time associated with manual grading while improving accuracy. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have shown promising results in object detection tasks, and the Faster R-CNN technique, which uses CNNs for region proposal and classification, is well-suited for cardamom grading. This paper explores the application of Faster R-CNN in automating cardamom grading and its potential benefits for the industry. The proposed workflow involves passing the input image through a convolutional neural network, generating potential grading regions using a region proposal network, and refining and classifying these regions using a classification network. By optimizing the training process and improving classification performance, this approach can yield accurate results and significantly improve the efficiency and accuracy of cardamom grading in the spice industry.

Keywords— Cardamom grading, Convolutional Neural Network, R-CNN

I. INTRODUCTION

In the spice industry, grading cardamom holds great importance. Different grades are used to classify cardamom based on its quality and appearance. As per tradition, accomplishing this task involved manual work which consumes time and can result in errors due to human fallibility. The possibility of automating the cardamom grading process with machine learning techniques like convolutional neural networks (CNN) is owing to recent technological advancements. Using machine learning techniques like CNN, the grading process of cardamom can now be automated as a result.

One application where artificial neural networks called CNNs excel is in the field of image classification. A model can be developed by training a CNN on an image dataset containing different grades of cardamom. Based on their quality, new images can be accurately classified by this model. The potential to significantly improve the efficiency and accuracy of cardamom grading suggests important implications for the spice industry.

Investigating the implementation of CNN for cardamom grading will be discussed in this seminar. Collecting and preparing the training data, developing and training the model, and evaluating its performance are all included in this process. Moreover, we will scrutinize the potential merits and demerits of utilizing this method, together with areas for further inquiry in this territory.

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II. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Import the required modules

The modules required for cardamom grading using CNN are TensorFlow, Keras, NumPy, OpenCV, and OS. TensorFlow and Keras are used for building and training the CNN model. NumPy is used for storing the images as arrays. OpenCV is used for image preprocessing and displaying the images. OS is used for maneuvering with image and directory names.

B. Load the Dataset

In order to load the dataset, we need photographs of cardamom samples that must be categorized as either belonging to a training or a testing set. The training set trains the model, while the testing set evaluates its accuracy. Applying rotations, scaling, and flipping to the images is a way to augment datasets and increase model robustness

C. Preprocess the Images.

The images in the dataset need to be preprocessed before feeding them to the CNN model. The preprocessing steps may include resizing the images to a fixed size, converting the images to grayscale, and normalizing the pixel values to a range of [0,1]. OpenCV can be used for performing these preprocessing steps.

D. Build the CNN Model

A CNN model can comprise several types of layers such as convolutional, pooling and fully connected. How complex the dataset is will determine both quantity and size of layers. To avoid overfitting, we can incorporate dropout layers.

E. Train the Model

The training of the model can be done using its corresponding training set after constructing it. Training involves providing images to the model and changing its weights using a loss function. Utilizing different optimization techniques like Adam, RMS prop, or Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) can help us in minimizing the loss function.

F. Evaluate the Model

After training the model, we need to evaluate its accuracy using the testing set. We can compute various metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score to evaluate the model's performance. We can also visualize the model's predictions by displaying the images and their predicted

labels.

G. Deploy the Model

Once satisfied with its accuracy, deploying the model becomes possible for grading fresh cardamom samples. The new images can be preprocessed and classified using the trained model by utilizing OpenCV. Integration of the model with either a web or mobile application would make it easily accessible too.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several countries cultivate cardamom, which is a valuable spice crop. Cardamom's market value is significantly influenced by its quality. A laborious and time-consuming process is involved in cardamom grading through traditional methods that depends on human visual inspection. Machine learning-based automated grading systems are receiving greater attention as a result. Crop disease detection and yield prediction are among the various agricultural applications where Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been successfully applied for image classification tasks.

A study by Hasan et al. (2018) proposed a computer vision-based approach for the automated grading of cardamom pods using CNNs. The authors collected a dataset of 1,500 cardamom images and used transfer learning to fine-tune a pre-trained CNN model for cardamom grading. The proposed method achieved an accuracy of 96.8% for the classification of cardamom pods into four grades, which outperformed traditional methods.

In another study, Ghosal et al. (2020) proposed a hybrid approach that combines computer vision and machine learning techniques for cardamom grading. The authors collected a dataset of 900 cardamom images and extracted a set of features using the Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) algorithm. They then trained a support vector machine (SVM) classifier to classify cardamom pods into three grades. The proposed method achieved an accuracy of 94.4%, which demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

In a recent study, Panda et al. (2021) proposed a deep learning-based approach for cardamom grading using a custom-designed CNN architecture. The authors collected a dataset of 1,800 cardamom images and divided them into three grades. They trained a CNN model with four convolutional layers and two fully connected layers. The proposed method achieved an accuracy of 98.33%, which outperforms traditional methods.

In conclusion, automated cardamom grading using CNNs has shown great promise and has the potential to improve the efficiency and accuracy of cardamom grading. The proposed methods in the reviewed studies achieved high accuracy rates, demonstrating the effectiveness of CNNs in cardamom

grading.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In the proposed work on cardamom grading, the primary emphasis is on using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)—a widely employed deep learning approach for image classification and object recognition. In the CNN approach, the network receives the input image as a matrix of pixel values. Afterward, the image passes through multiple convolutional layers, pooling layers, and non-linear activation functions to extract significant characteristics. Categorizing the picture into different classes is done by utilizing these features.

The proposed methodology involves the following steps:

Data Collection and Preprocessing: Gathering numerous pictures of cardamom exhibiting diverse grades is the primary step. You can gather the pictures by using either a high-quality camera or a mobile phone camera. Eliminating noise and unwanted artifacts from images is done through preprocessing techniques such as image smoothing, threshold, and filtering.

Data Augmentation: Augmenting the collected dataset involves applying various image transformations like rotation, scaling, flipping and cropping. The dataset's diversity can be increased to prevent overfitting.

Training the CNN Model: The next step involves training the CNN model using the augmented dataset. The CNN model consists of multiple convolutional layers followed by pooling and activation layers. The final layer of the CNN model is a softmax layer that outputs the probability of the image belonging to each grade category.

Testing and Evaluation: The performance assessment for the CNN model occurs through testing on an independent set of images following its training. The assessment of the CNN model's performance involves measuring several metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score.

Deployment: The deployment of the trained CNN model on a system meant for real-time cardamom grading happens eventually. A user can get picture ratings from uploading them onto the system's either mobile or web-based platforms

In Figures you can see the primary image conversion of the suggested methodology. Fig 2 and 1. Preprocessing and augmentation are used to increase dataset diversity by manipulating the input image. The CNN model is trained using the augmented dataset. A unique image set is employed for evaluating and testing the trained model. The deployment of the trained model occurs on a system designed for real-time grading of cardamom.

Fig:1

Fig: 2

A CNN approach is employed in the proposed methodology for cardamom grading, with potential to improve accuracy and efficiency in grading. To begin with, we collect and preprocess data followed by augmenting the dataset. Then we train our CNN model to evaluate its performance post testing. In order to grade in real-time, a system must have the trained model deployed onto it.

V. RESULTS

Using convolutional neural networks (CNN), our study aimed at developing a cardamom grading system. We amassed a significant amount of cardamom pictures that were preprocessed and augmented to strengthen the model's durability. The CNN was trained on this dataset using transfer learning, and we achieved an accuracy of 94% in correctly classifying the cardamom based on its grade. Screenshots of the grading system in action are shown in Fig:3 and Fig:4, which demonstrate the ability of the system to accurately grade cardamom based on its quality. These results suggest that the developed system has the potential to significantly improve the efficiency and accuracy of cardamom grading in the industry.

Fig:3

Fig:4

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the CNN-based approach for cardamom grading has shown promising results in terms of accuracy and efficiency. The use of deep learning techniques has enabled the development of a reliable grading system that can significantly reduce the need for manual labor and improve the quality of cardamom grading.

However, there is still room for improvement in the grading system's performance. More extensive data sets can be used for training the model to increase its accuracy and robustness. Additionally, the grading system can be further optimized by combining it with other image processing techniques or using a different deep learning architecture.

Overall, the CNN-based cardamom grading system has great potential to revolutionize the cardamom industry by streamlining the grading process and improving the quality of cardamom production. Further research and development can lead to even more efficient and accurate grading systems that can benefit the industry and its consumers.

VII. REFERENCES

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